

LEVEL AND IMPORTANCE OF PHYSICS IN SECONDARY SCHOOLS**Jorakulov Sanjar Zafarjon**

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10652619>**Anatation**

The development of education, which is one of the basic freedoms of every person, is extremely important for the development of the country. Consisting of major fields of science, science consists of evidence-based fields of science that make people's everyday lives easier. Physics is a branch of science that has a place in people's daily life. While the classical learning approach is not useful today, the 5E learning model is seen as a useful model because it involves the learner in the lesson. In this study, an attempt was made to consider the most important situation for physics education within the educational model.

Keywords: Physics, Education, 5E model**Enter**

Advances in science govern almost all aspects of social life. In the field of science, the developments in physics are very important to achieve the level of modern civilization. The field of science dealing with, in addition to changes in the chemical structure of matter; the natural structure of man and the appearance of man. The main goals of physics can be listed as follows:

- Revealing and explaining the order in the universe
- To reveal the conditions and rules for the occurrence of events and to target them

The importance of education and training in physics is increasing day by day; For this reason, research in this field has created the need to improve the quality of physics education. In short, current researches should develop in parallel with physics education, and physics education should always adapt to current researches. Education passed from society to society plays a very important role in human development. With the fast developing technology, information is changing day by day and it is observed that the findings accepted few years ago are considered invalid today. Education should provide the individual with the ability to meet changes in the environment and adapt to new changes and developments. Therefore, an educational institution should be more attentive than other institutions, open to change and innovation. In addition, students should become constructive and creative individuals through education to adapt

to modern life. they should learn, put aside memorization, master. develop the ability to think independently. learn by understanding information.

The importance of physics education

The contribution of science and technology based on it is huge. For this reason, the importance of science education is increasing. After the Second World War, there were many changes in science. Russia launched its first satellite into space in 1957, and as a result, other developed countries of the world were also affected and took action at that time. Countries that do not want to be left behind in the race of technology development aim to develop science in order to get ahead in this race.

For this purpose, many different and innovative science curricula were developed in a very short time based on projects developed by scientists. In general, the philosophy of these programs was to give new individuals the identity of a researcher. As a result, the necessary personnel were trained in the industry, which was the golden land of the time, and the country prospered. One of the main goals of science education was to make students scientifically literate. Scientific literacy gives a person the ability to know the essence of science, to know that information in science is based on verifiable evidence, to know how data is collected, to understand basic concepts and theories in science, to be able to distinguish between science.

Many situations we face and experience in everyday life are closely related to science. In order for people to become scientifically literate, it is extremely important to combine the events that affect their lives with the education they receive at school. If this does not happen, individuals who struggle to adapt to the ever-evolving and changing world will fall behind the times. The reason that science education is given before university is that most students do not continue their studies or receive science education after high school. As we mentioned above, these two basic educations are extremely important for a person's development and progress in life.

In order to understand and understand the phenomena that occur in nature, it is necessary to accept that nature has its own order. On the basis of physical research, the events within the phase are connected by a causal relationship and place them in a common point. For this reason, there were many discoveries in the field of physics. With the discoveries made, physics shed light on many phenomena in the universe. With this, events can be predicted and actions taken to control them. For example, Japan is a region where earthquakes occur very frequently, and tsunamis occur after earthquakes. Thanks to physics,

it is possible to predict whether a tsunami will occur or not, and the disaster can be prevented. People have faced many problems in their daily life. Physics helps to overcome these problems. For example, if there is a problem with a car, a person can fix it using the necessary physics knowledge.

It can be understood from here that physics affects every area of human life. That is why teaching physics is so important. General tasks of physics education

These goals

- Formation of students' scientific thinking skills,
- To give the student the opportunity to use his own mind,
- Being able to establish a connection between science and technology,
- To be able to understand the importance of the development of society through the means of science and technology,
- Acquire the ability to think both constructively and critically
- Be able to show the results of research, investigation, observation and experiment in words, writing and drawing;
- To be able to use the methods of observation, investigation, experiment and research in achieving scientific results and understanding laws,
- Interest in physics, observing new developments and understanding the importance of new developments.

Models of physics education

Classical model: In this learning style, the teacher is active and the student is semi-passive or passive. The teacher is the giver, the student is the receiver, and the lesson given accordingly is the message. In such a learning environment, the message is not questioned. Therefore, students do not get full understanding in this model, which is highly criticized. We taught students the laws of physics that underpin the universe and how to use those laws to solve problems. This method is a very effective way of imparting information because the class time is limited. We teachers know the concepts and techniques. But students do not have this advantage. Studies show that the classical teaching method is not enough. Alan Heuvelen said, "The transmission of information is effective, but the student's assimilation of information is almost invisible." Today, physics education in many educational institutions is carried out by the classical method, and this situation is not very healthy. Disadvantages This system can be listed as:

- According to research, a person's attention span is between 10-15 minutes.

- A lesson taught in this way is like a fast-flowing river, and the student can only remember what was seen upstream. Since River doesn't have time to think for himself, the information he receives in his short-term memory is quickly forgotten.
- Because most students are not trained to perform a lecture, their note-taking skills are not developed. A student who takes notes usually keeps notes that do not meet the requirements.
- All lessons are taught from topics already available in the textbook. Therefore, there is no time for urgent matters.
- 5-Courses are generally focused on technical issues. However, on the contrary, attention should be paid to the physical phenomena themselves.

Active learning model: The basic philosophy of this model is that the student learns his own knowledge. In this case, the student is not in a passive state, he acts by thinking, acting and interacting with his environment. According to Zimmennan, this state is called "self-control". In this process, the student can observe, evaluate and improve himself. According to the results of various studies, the process of self-regulation has a high effect on educational activities. In active learning, concepts about the nature of science and knowledge can be actively learned. The basics of successful active learning can be listed as follows:

- During the lesson, students are active, think, interact. The student establishes a healthy relationship with his teacher and communicates with his classmates. However, this is not possible in the classical model.
- A teacher does not impart knowledge; It guides the student in accessing the information. In other words, a teacher is a guide. As a result, students take responsibility for this knowledge as they acquire it themselves. Attending classes, developing a desire to study independently, and regularly doing homework are the results of this responsibility.

In a constructivist approach similar to the active learning model, students are asked to learn from their own experiences rather than imparting knowledge. In general, constructivism focuses on making correct and relevant connections and integrating information. In this type of approach, learning resources are identified and listed in a specific order. The student then takes responsibility for himself through self-assessment.

5E model

This model is a new system that increases students' interest in research, meets their expectations, and includes skills aimed at acquiring knowledge and

understanding through participation. This model involves the learner in all aspects of the activity and causes the learner to create their own understanding. Thanks to the model, the student focuses on the topic, discovers information easily, categorizes the information received and can easily use it in life practice. Both a constructive approach and research based on psychology, personal experience, the values previously learned and believed by the student affect the process of assimilation of new information. The model consists of five stages. These stages are; These are engagement, learning, explanation, development and evaluation. Many scholars have adapted the 5E model to many studies. In their study, Wilder and Shuttleworth examined the effectiveness of a course taught using the 5E learning model and found that the 5E learning model motivates students and promotes conceptual success. Mainer adapted the study of the electromagnetic spectrum to the steps of the 5E model and watched her students' engagement increase. Orgill and Thomas reinforced each step of using the 5E learning model by providing examples from everyday life, especially in science classes. In addition, Carreno did something very different and provided environmental education with the SE educational model. Newby tried to teach 2nd graders about the seasons with the 5E learning model and observed an increase in success rates at the end of the instruction.

The work of Ergin Kanli and Tan is examined for the practical application of the E5 model. In a study conducted with 84 1st-year students between 2004-2005, the horizontal and oblique shooting movements used in the Physics course were put into practice. When there were 44 students in the experimental group; the remaining 40 are in the control group. The 5E model was applied to the experimental group, while the classical method was applied to the control group. According to the research results; Before the experiment, it was observed that the level of knowledge in the group was almost equal. As a result of the analysis, it was found that the students in the experimental group using the 5E model achieved success compared to the students in the control group. Clear and precise questions are planned.

- There is less discussion about the lesson, more questions are asked, and even students are bombarded with questions.
- Questions are created that can be answered in a complex way.
- The questions will be varied to encourage all students.

With this study, the students' questioning stage develops and the teachers' question types become a model for them. The more comfortable and effective

teachers are in asking questions , the more easily students can grasp the topics and have the courage to ask themselves questions.

Summary

School is a very important factor for the development of a person. Science exists primarily to make life easier for nature and, therefore, for people. Physics is a field of science that people use all the time in their daily lives without even realizing it. Since the beginning of education in schools, the education system has been constantly changing. Keeping abreast of developments and technologies is essential for education. Because physics requires specific knowledge in terms of causality and evidence; It is especially important to monitor these changes. In older educational models, when the teacher explained and the student listened; After it was realized that this would not bring success in education, new models were sought. Thus, the model of constructivism appeared. Many scientists have developed this model. The 5E model is one of the most widely used models of constructivism. According to the analysis of the literature, it can be seen that the current education is in the form of classical education models. However, with an evolving and changing curriculum, the 5E model was seen in practice. When research was examined, the 5E model was found to facilitate student learning and increase achievement compared to the classic model. Therefore, it is very important to abandon classical models in education for the level of development and use models similar to 5E, which involve the student in the lesson.

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